

A comparative study of properties of ZnO and CdO thin filmsS. S. Karande^{a-b}, R. J. Deokate^c, J. V. Thombare^b and V. M. Bhuse^{a*},^a Department of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Nagpur MS-440001, India^b Department of Physics, Dr. Ganpatrao Deshmukh Mahavidyalaya, Sangola, Tal-Sangola, Dist-Solapur, MS-413307, India.^c Department of Physics, Vidya Pratishthans's, Arts, Science and Commerce College, Baramati MS-413 133, India.

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Abstract: ZnO and CdO thin films were prepared on pre-cleaned glass substrates by the chemical bath deposition (CBD) method at 300 K. The thin films were annealed in the air for 1 hr at annealing temperature 400°C were subjected for structural properties investigations using X-ray diffraction (XRD); morphological study by means of scanning electron microscopy (SEM); and for optical properties investigations using ultraviolet-visible-near-infrared (UV-VIS-NIR) spectroscopy. XRD results showed that both ZnO and CdO films exhibit crystalline nature. SEM studies revealed the formation of nanosheets like structure for ZnO and sunflower like structure for CdO thin film. Electrical resistivity measurement at 300 K showed that the electrical resistivity of both oxides thin films were of the order of $10^{12} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$ was found to decrease with a temperature rise, indicating the normal semiconductor behavior. Furthermore, the optical investigations including band gap energy, extinction coefficient, refractive index and optical conductivity etc, have been investigated and compared with each other. The direct band gap energy values were observed 3.7 eV and 2.7 eV for ZnO and CdO thin film, respectively.

Keywords: ZnO, CdO, XRD, SEM, semiconductor behavior, optical properties.

1. Introduction:

Transparent conducting oxide (TCO) is semiconductor oxide that is optically transparent and electrically conductive material that finds its uses in liquid crystal displays, photovoltaic devices, transparent surfaces in touch panels, organic light emitting diodes, flat panel displays and sensors [1-5]. Further, high transparency (over 85%) in visible portion of the spectrum with forbidden energy gap greater than 3 eV, better electrical conductivity enables their use in the field of transparent optoelectronics. The TCOs are classified into two groups based upon type of charge carriers as p-type TCOs and n-type TCOs [5]. The materials studied for p-type TCOs are NiO, CuAlO₂, CuScO, CuYO, CuInO, CuGaO, CuCrO, SrCuO, LaCuOS, Mg doped CuCrO, ZnO [5]. The materials studied for n-type TCOs are Fe-SnO₂, In-SnO₂, ZnO-SnO₂, CdO-SnO₂, ZnO-In₂O₃,

ZnO, CdO, SnO, InO_{1.5} and GaO_{1.5} to obtain Zn and Cd based tin oxides, Zn and Ga based indium oxides [5]. The oxides of Cd exhibit better characteristics but their use is restricted because of their toxicity. The indium tin oxide (ITO), find large applications amongst all n-type TCOs, because of the highest conductivity and transparency, but the cost concern restricts their use for industrial applications. Therefore, efforts are being made to find an alternative to ITOs.

ZnO is mostly studied member of TCOs. Researchers are trying to fabricate of p-ZnO based TCOs, which plays important role in "Transparent Electronics", and providing a wide forbidden energy gap for p-n homo-junctions [5].

Additionally, cadmium oxide (CdO) is most studied metal-oxide having n-type conductivity and direct band gap between 2.2 to 2.5 eV. Beside this, it has

low resistivity and better optical transmittance within the visible range of the solar spectrum. Hence, it has been studied in various applications like UV absorbers, gas sensors, automobile exhaust catalysts, solar cells, catalysis, photodiodes, oxygen storage materials, fuel cells and phototransistors [6-8]. ZnO is a well-known material for wide bandgap energy special chemical, optical as well as electrical properties. Such properties made essential in future applications like latest optoelectronic devices, piezoelectric transducers, solar cell, sensors, catalysis and other applications etc. [9-14]. CdO and ZnO thin films have been deposited by various physical and chemical methods. But chemical methods give some additional benefit as cost effective and easy synthesis. Hence, CBD method is adapted to synthesis of Zn and Cd based oxides thin films. The CBD of CdO and ZnO thin films nanostructures on substrates ensures high rate and regularity over the entire area of the samples.

In the present study, efforts have been taken to fabricate ZnO as well as CdO based transparent conducting oxide thin films through a CBD method. We reported herein the details of synthesis and characterization of ZnO and CdO based transparent oxide semiconductor film by means of structural, morphological, semiconducting behavior and optical properties.

2. Experimental details:

2.1 Film deposition

CdO and ZnO based thin films were prepared by CBD method at 300 K. The synthesis of CdO thin film was carried as follows: To an aqueous 0.1 M CdCl₂ solution, ammonia solution was added to obtain the precipitate of Cd(OH)₂, hereafter the dropwise addition was continued to achieve a homogeneous solution and the pH of resultant solution was maintained at ~ 11 to 12 with sufficient ammonia solution

addition. Cleaned glass substrates were immersed in resultant solution and the resultant solution was maintained at unstirred condition for 72 hrs at 300 K [15]. The deposited samples were rinsed with double distilled water to lose any adhered particles. At 673 K, the samples films were annealed in air for 1 hrs and used for various characterizations. Similarly, for ZnO thin films was prepared by using aqueous 0.1 M ZnCl₂ solution by following the same methodology. The deposited films were rinsed with distilled water, air annealed at 573 K for 1 hrs and used for various characterization.

2.2 Characterization Techniques

Structural and crystallographic properties of films were studied by X-ray diffractometer (XRD Bruker AXS D8 Advance model) with the Cu-K_α (λ = 1.5406 Å) radiation source in the 2θ range 20°-80°. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Model: JEOL JSM-6360) assembly was used to study surface morphology of ZnO and CdO films. The electrical resistivity measurement of ZnO and CdO films was held using dc two-point probe method. Silver paste was used to form ohmic contacts. To study the optical parameters, UV-visible spectroscopy (UV-1800 Shimadzu Uv-Vis-NIR Spectrophotometer) in the wavelength range 200-1100 nm at room temperature has been used.

3. Result and discussion

3.1 X-Ray diffraction study

An XRD technique provides the information about the phase and the crystallinity of the films. The mean crystallite size was calculated using Scherrer formula [16].

$$D = \frac{0.9\lambda}{\beta \cdot \cos\theta} \quad \text{-----(1)}$$

Where θ-the Bragg's angle, β-Full Width at Half Maximum (FWHM) in radians. Figure (1a) represents XRD pattern

of ZnO thin film. The film exhibited polycrystalline nature with cubic structure and proved the peaks corresponding to the pattern exhibited in JCPDS card 03-65-2908. The ZnO thin film presented leading diffraction peaks at 2θ values of (33.02° , 38.43° , 55.44° , 66.10° , 82.15° and 94.49°) associated with the diffraction from the planes (111), (200), (220), (311), (222) and (400) respectively. The XRD pattern obtained for CdO thin film is displayed in figure 1(b). The CdO film showed a polycrystalline structure with cubic structure [JCPDS card 20.179]. The diffraction peaks at 2θ values of 33.18° , 38.50° , 55.65° and 66.17° have been assigned as the diffraction from (111), (200), (220) and (311) miller planes of the cubic CdO.

Figure 1: (a) XRD pattern of ZnO thin film; (b) XRD pattern of CdO thin film.

3.2 Surface morphological study

The surface morphology of ZnO and CdO thin films as analyzed from SEM is shown in Fig 2(a-b) and Fig 2(c-d), respectively. A Fig 2(a-b) exhibit the ZnO structures at different magnifications consisting of flower like texture consisting of randomly oriented porous nanosheet on the whole substrate, this type of morphology is quite essential for performing electrochemical activities. The figure 2(c,d) at different magnifications show homogeneous distribution of nanogranules over the whole surface, .

Figure 2: (a-b) SEM images of ZnO thin film; (c-d) SEM images of CdO thin film.

3.3 Electrical resistivity

The electrical resistivity of ZnO and CdO films were measured using standard DC two-probe method in the temperature range of 323–423K. The Fig. 3 shows the variations electrical resistivity ($\log p$) of ZnO and CdO films with reciprocal of absolute temperature ($1000/T$). The room temperature resistivity was found to be high; it can be attributed to the dislocations and imperfections resulted in films. The electrical resistivity of both samples was found to be decreased with temperature, indicating the semiconductor behavior. The decrease in resistivity was observed due to minimization of defects structural dislocations, disorders

and surface imperfections in the films. The observed results are supported by other studies [17]. The graph of both films presents two linear parts; first in the lower temperature range (323–370 K), with a small slope and another in the higher temperature range (370–423 K), with large slope, indicating the different mechanism of conduction at different temperature range in the films. The activation energies were calculated using the relation;

$$\rho = \rho_0 \exp\left(\frac{E_a}{kT}\right) \quad \text{--- (2)}$$

Figure 3: (a) Resistivity measurement of ZnO thin film; (b) Resistivity measurement of CdO thin film.

In low temperature region, the value of activation energy were found to be 0.38 eV and 0.26 eV for ZnO and CdO films, respectively, where grain boundary scattering may be predominant. In high temperature region, the value of activation energy were found to be 0.27 and 0.22 eV for ZnO and CdO films, respectively corresponding to hopping type conduction mechanism. The activation energy values confirmed the semiconductor behavior.

3.4 Optical spectroscopy study

The Fig. 4(a-b) shows the absorbance and the transmittance spectra of the Zn and Cd based oxide thin films respectively. The ZnO thin film presented maximum absorbance towards the shorter wavelength side ($\lambda < 400$ nm), while decreased around the wavelength region ($\lambda \sim 900$ nm). A CdO thin film exhibits more absorbance wavelength ($\lambda < 600$ nm), which decreases endlessly just before wavelength region ($\lambda \sim 900$ nm). The absorption coefficient (α) was calculated using the relation (3) [18-19];

$$\alpha = \frac{1}{d} \ln \left[\frac{T}{(1-R)^2} \right] \quad \text{----- (3)}$$

Where, R - reflectance, T –transmittance, d - thickness of film. The fig 4 (c) shows the variation in absorption coefficient corresponding to photon energy. The figure shows the very small absorption coefficient of the order of 10^5 cm^{-1} in the visible and near-IR region. This can be attributed to the onset of inter-band transitions at the fundamental edge [20].

Figure 4: (a) Absorbance spectra of ZnO and CdO thin films; (b) Transmittance spectra of ZnO and CdO thin films; (c) The absorption coefficient versus wavelength for the ZnO and CdO thin films; (d) Reflectance spectra of ZnO and CdO thin films.

Figure 4(c) exhibits a long tail at the highwavelengthside. The absorption for ZnO thin film increases slowly with incident photon energy, while forCdO thin film increases rapidly. At photon energies $h\nu > 2.5$ eV; comparatively, the absorption coefficient spectra exhibited a steeper increase for CdO thin film than that ofZnO thin film. The rapid increase in absorption coefficient may be due to interband transition from the deep level electrons of the valence band.The relation between optical parameters like A, T and Rprovides total reflectance of Zn and Cd based oxide thin films and calculated using equation (4) [21];

$$R = \left[1 - \left(\frac{T}{\exp(-A)} \right) \right]^{1/2} \quad \text{---- (4)}$$

The Figure 4 (d) exhibitsthe reflectancespectra ofZn and Cd based oxide thin filmswith the reflectance for both of the thin filmsexhibiting less than 1 %.

The Forbidden energy gap E_g can be measured using experimental values of absorption coefficient by varyingphoton energy $h\nu$, by means of (5) [21],

$$(\alpha h\nu)^n = A(h\nu - E_g) \quad \text{---- (5)}$$

Where α -the absorption coefficient, $h\nu$ - the photon energy, n - the exponent, n has value $1/2$ for indirect transitions, similarly n has value 2 for direct transitions, for the transition A will be probabilistic parameter and E_g forbidden energy gap.

Figure 5: (a) Plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy $(h\nu)$ of ZnO and CdO thin films gives band gap energy; (b) Plot of extinction coefficient versus wavelength for ZnO and CdO thin films; (c) Refractive index of ZnO and CdO thin films; (d) The plot of refractive index factor $(n^2-1)^{-1}$ versus reciprocal of square of $(h\nu)$.

The plot of $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus $(h\nu)$ shown in Figure 5(a). The forbidden energy gap values are 3.7 eV and 2.7 eV for ZnO and CdO respectively. The value of forbidden energy gap of CdO thin film is 2.7 eV, which is greater than the reported values [22-25] and matching with earlier report [26]. The greater value of forbidden energy gap may be due to quantum confinement effect via clusters of the size of bulk exciton Bohr radius [26].

For both the oxide films, refractive index (n) was estimated by relation (6), while the extinction coefficient (k) of ZnO and CdO thin films was calculated using the relation (7) as given below [27-28];

$$n = \frac{1+R}{1-R} + \left[\frac{4R}{(1-R)^2} - k^2 \right]^{1/2} \quad \text{---- (6)}$$

where R - the reflectance and (k) - the extinction coefficient (it is measure of the fraction of light scattering loss and absorption per unit distance of the medium penetration of materials).

$$k = \frac{\alpha\lambda}{4\pi} \quad \text{---- (7)}$$

Figure 5(b) is a graph of extinction coefficient (k_0) vs. the wavelength (λ). The Figure 5(b) illustrates the overall variation in (k_0) over entire spectra and indicates maxima value at 500–650 nm. Further decreased to higher wavelengths, resulting the direct relation is very easy to absorption of light. Low values (0.002–0.001 for ZnO;; 0.005-0.007 for CdO) indicates the considerable absorbance of both oxide thin films.

A graph of refractive index (n) vs photon energy ($h\nu$) is plotted in Figure 5(c). In the range of 1.2eV to 2.7 eV of photon energy ($h\nu$), refractive indices (n) changes from 19 to 4 for both samples, and becomes stable after 2.7 eV of photon energy ($h\nu$). The single oscillator parameters as Wemple–DiDomenic(WDD) dispersion parameter (E_0), static refractive index (n_0), dispersion energy (E_d), etc. were evaluated by relation (8)[29-30]:

$$n^2(h\nu) = 1 + \frac{E_0 E_d}{E_0^2 - (h\nu)^2} \quad \text{---- (8)}$$

Where, (n) -the refractive index, (E_0) - the single oscillator energy, (E_d) - the dispersion energy which is the strength of inter band optical transition. The values of E_0 and E_d were estimated using the graph of $(n^2 - 1)^{-1}$ versus $(h\nu)^2$ as shown in Fig. 5d, the intercept on Y-axis provides the value of E_0/E_d and the slope of the line provides the value of $1/(E_0 \cdot E_d)$. The estimated values of E_0 and E_d are tabulated in the Table 1. Using these values (E_0 and E_d), the static refractive index (n_0) was calculated by (9):

$$n_0 = \sqrt{\left(1 + \frac{E_d}{E_0}\right)} \quad \text{---- (9)}$$

The values of (n_0) can be calculated by extrapolating the WDD equation (9) to $h\nu \rightarrow 0$ and tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: The band gaps and the estimated values of the oscillator parameters E_0 and E_d as well as other related optical parameters extrapolated from WDD model.

Sample	E_d (eV)	E_0 (eV)	n_0	E_g (eV)	E_0/E_d
ZnO	25.00	4	2.69	3.73	0.160
CdO	20.44	3.76	2.53	2.75	0.184

The interaction of electromagnetic wave with optoelectronic material is studied with the help of dielectric behavior. The dielectric constant composed of real part and imaginary part. The real part of dielectric constant gives information about the decrement in speed of electromagnetic wave in material. The imaginary part of dielectric constant provides the information about absorption of electromagnetic energy to dipole motion. The real dielectric constant (ϵ_r) and imaginary dielectric constant (ϵ_i) can be evaluated by using the values of refractive index (n) and extinction coefficient (k_0) by using the following relations [31-32]:

$$\epsilon_0 = n^2 - k_0^2 \quad \text{---- (10)}$$

$$\epsilon_r = 2nk_0 \quad \text{---- (11)}$$

Figure 6 (a-b) gives the changes in (ϵ_r) and (ϵ_i) as a function of electromagnetic energy ($h\nu$). The values of ϵ_r are higher than ϵ_i and both curves decreases exponentially with electromagnetic energy. Comparatively, ϵ_r is higher for CdO thin film than that of ZnO thin films, may be due to greater value of refractive index.

The optical response of ZnO and CdO thin film is recorded in terms of optical conductivity. The optical conductivity of the

ZnO and CdO thin film can be calculated by the relation (12), where c is the velocity of light [33]:

$$\sigma = \frac{\alpha n c}{4\pi} \quad \text{---- (12)}$$

Figure 6: (a) Variation of real dielectric constant with respect to photon energy of ZnO and CdO thin films; (b) Variation of imaginary dielectric constant with respect to photon energy of ZnO and CdO thin films.

Figure 7 provides the nature of optical conductivity (σ) as a function of wavelength (λ). Plot showed that larger values (of the order of 10^{14} s^{-1}) of the optical conductivity in the lower wavelength (i.e. higher energy) range and slightly decreasing from the absorption edge region to the longer

wavelength. Comparatively, optical conductivity is higher for CdO thin film than that of ZnO thin films. This is may be due to forbidden energy gap of CdO thin film. As photon incident on CdO thin film, then more sites will be active than that of ZnO thin film. Also, we may assign as; high optical absorbance and low extinction coefficient leads to excitation of the electrons [33-35]. For low energy photon, optical conductivity is constant for CdO and ZnO thin films.

Figure 7: Optical conductivity of ZnO and CdO thin films as a function of wavelength.

4. Conclusions:

In conclusion, ZnO and CdO thin films have been deposited using simple and low-cost chemical bath deposition method and structural, optical, electrical and thermo electrical properties are studied. The XRD results obtained polycrystalline nature of the films with cubic crystal structure. The SEM study presented the nanostructure surface morphology. The optical study proved direct band gap nature with band gap energy 3.7 and 2.7 eV for ZnO and CdO thin film respectively. The electrical results showed that semiconducting nature of films and suitable for optoelectronic devices. The optical parameters like refractive index, extinction coefficient, real and imaginary dielectric constants were calculated and

reported. The changes in real as well as imaginary parts of dielectric constants as a function of incident photon energy verified strong interactions between the incident photons and the free electrons.

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